

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE FREQUENCY OF ZYGOMATICOFACIAL FORAMINA IN MALE AND FEMALE SKULLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7989663>

Abstract

A detailed study of the anatomy of the skeleton of the facial part of the skull is impossible without taking into account the zygomatic bone. The zygomaticofacial foramen belonging to this bone is characterized by excessive variability in quantitative terms, which complicates the implementation of high-quality anesthesia in this area. The material for the study was 32 male and 38 female skulls belonging to the adult age period (21–60 years), stored in the craniological collection of the Museum of the Department of Human Anatomy and Medical Terminology of **Azerbaijan Medical University**. Zygomaticofacial foramina are defined as follows: absent, a single large foramen, one large and any number of smaller foramina, two large foramina, two large foramina and any number of smaller foramina, a single small foramen, multiple small foramina (by Jane E. Buikstra and Douglas H. Ubelaker, 1994). On 2 male and 2 female skulls, the zygomatic bones were destroyed, respectively, on the right and left sides; thus, the number of skulls examined to determine the quantitative variants of the zygomaticofacial foramina was as follows: 31 male (45.6%) and 37 (54.4%) female skulls. An analysis of the data obtained shows that the most common quantitative variant is a single large foramen on the left side, both for male and female skulls (38.7% and 54.1%, respectively). The absence of the zygomaticofacial foramen more often characterizes the right zygomatic bone in male and female skulls; on male skulls, the zygomaticofacial foramen was absent on the right side in 35.5% of all skulls studied. In female skulls, the absence of a foramen was found on the right side in 37.8% of the examined skulls. Multiple small foramina is the least common quantitative variant found on the left for male skulls (1 skull, 3.2%); on female skulls, this variant was not found at all. One large and any number of smaller foramina is the least common quantitative variant that characterizes the right zygomatic bones in men. In women, the least common variant, according to our study, is a single small foramen (1 skull, 2.7%). This quantitative variant is found on the left.

Keywords: zygomaticofacial foramen, skulls, absence of the zygomaticofacial foramen, a single large foramen.

Introduction. The zygomatic surface of the zygomatic bone is convex and perforated near its center with a small opening, the zygomaticofacial foramen, through which the branch of the same name and the vessels that reach the face pass [1, p. 1505; 2, p. 23]. Data on the location and change in the number of zygomaticofacial foramina are important for preventing damage to the zygomatic nerve and vessel during surgery, but due to the large variability found in the zygomaticofacial foramina, it is an unreliable guide for maxillofacial surgery [3, p. 559-62; 4, p. 168-171].

The opinion of [5, p. 1035-1041] somewhat contradicts the above. In his opinion, the clinical significance of the variability in the location and number of the zygomaticofacial foramen lies both in the use of this

foramen as a guide for osteotomy in maxillofacial and craniofacial interventions and in the possibility of damage (during operations on the zygomatic bone) of the structures emerging from it. Surgeons must be aware of this anatomical variation to minimize the risk of complications.

The zygomaticofacial foramen ranged from a complete absence to four small foramina. A single foramen was observed in half of the cases [6, p. 168-72]. The position and frequency of the zygomaticofacial foramina can vary between individuals and between two sides of the facial skeleton in the same individual. The zygomaticofacial foramina are very common structures that tend to appear alone [7, p. 823-830]. In addition,

the zygomaticofacial foramen is an anatomical structure that should be considered when performing retrobulbar anesthesia, especially given the differences in technique among ophthalmologists [8, p. 275-7].

In the zygomatic bones, differences are revealed in the number of foramina on their orbital and facial surfaces. The location of the zygomaticofacial foramen may vary by population, and knowledge of their location is important in stabilizing zygomatic fractures during an endoscopic subperiosteal facelift [9, p.96-9; 10, p. 419-21].

A detailed study of the zygomaticofacial foramen depending on the shape of the skull (cephalic index) can be found in [11, p. 245-251]. According to this work, in mesocephalic skulls, the foramina are, in most cases, located in a "chain" corresponding to the lower outer margin of the orbit. In dolichocephalic skulls, zygomaticofacial foramina are grouped not only in the region adjacent to the lower outer edge of the orbit; in brachycephalic skulls, most of the zygomaticofacial foramina are concentrated at the lower outer edge of the orbit.

A general review of the literature data shows that there are not enough works devoted directly to the zygomaticofacial foramen; particularly scarce information can be found on the topic of variations in the zygomaticofacial foramen and sex differences in this anatomical structure. Based on the foregoing, we carried out work to determine the frequency of anatomical variations in the number of zygomaticofacial foramen.

Materials and research methods. The material for the study was 32 male and 38 female skulls belonging to the adult age period (21–60 years), stored in the craniological collection of the Museum of the Department of Human Anatomy and Medical Terminology of Azerbaijan Medical University. The study used the cranioscopic method. Zygomaticofacial foramina are defined as follows: absent, a single large foramen, one large and any number of smaller foramina, two large foramina, two large foramina and any number of smaller foramina, a single small foramen, multiple small foramina (by Jane E. Buikstra and Douglas H. Ubelaker, 1994).

On 2 male and 2 female skulls, the zygomatic bones were destroyed, respectively, on the right and left sides; thus, the number of skulls examined to determine the quantitative variants of the zygomaticofacial foramina was as follows: 31 male (45.6%) and 37 (54.4%) female skulls. In all cases, the patency of the zygomaticofacial foramen was checked with a thin wire. The study was conducted under normal lighting; in case of difficulties in identifying the zygomaticofacial foramen for various reasons (small size of the foramen, changes in the color of the bone, complicating the detection of the foramen, etc.), artificial lighting was used and the study field was enlarged with a magnifying glass.

Results. The results of the study showed that the variations in the amount of zygomaticofacial foramina are very diverse. Thus, the zygomaticofacial foramen was absent in 11 male skulls (35.5%). The absence of the left zygomaticofacial foramen was found in 9 skulls (29.0%). A single large foramen was found on nine male skulls on the right (29.0%) and 12 on the left

(38.7%). One large and any number of smaller foramina were found on 1 male skull on the right (3.2%) and on 4 male skulls on the left (12.9%). Two large foramina were studied by us on five male skulls on the right (16.1%) and on three male skulls on the left (9.7%).

It should be noted that two large foramina and any number of smaller foramina were not found on either male or female skulls.

A single small foramen on male skulls was found as follows: 5 on the right (16.1%) and 2 on the left (6.5%). Multiple small foramina were found only on one male skull and only on the left (3.2%). This quantitative variant of the zygomaticofacial foramen was not found in female skulls.

The study of quantitative variations of the zygomaticofacial foramen on female skulls showed the following: the zygomaticofacial foramen was absent in 14 female skulls on the right (37.8%) and 11 on the left (29.7%). A single large foramen was found on 12 female skulls on the right (32.4%) and 20 female skulls on the left (54.1%). Two large foramina were studied and found on female skulls as follows: six female skulls (16.2%) on the right and five female skulls on the left (13.5%). A single small foramen was found on 5 female skulls on the right (13.5%) and 1 female skull on the left (2.7%).

An analysis of the data obtained shows that the most common quantitative variant is a single large foramen on the left side, both for male and female skulls (38.7% and 54.1%, respectively). The absence of the zygomaticofacial foramen more often characterizes the right zygomatic bone in male and female skulls; on male skulls, the zygomaticofacial foramen was absent on the right side in 35.5% of all skulls studied.

In female skulls, the absence of a foramen was found on the right side in 37.8% of the examined skulls. Multiple small foramina is the least common quantitative variant found on the left for male skulls (1 skull, 3.2%); on female skulls, this variant was not found at all. One large and any number of smaller foramina is the least common quantitative variant that characterizes the right zygomatic bones in men. In women, the least common variant, according to our study, is a single small foramen (1 skull, 2.7%). This quantitative variant is found on the left.

Discussion. As noted, the position as well as the frequency of the zygomaticofacial foramina vary between individuals. In particular, this variation is shown on two sides of the facial skeleton of the skull on the same individual. It is indicated that the zygomaticofacial foramina are very common structures that are mostly observed to be alone [7, p. 823-830]. According to our data, it characterizes the male and female skulls only from the left side. We have to note that the term "alone" should be exact because, in our work, we used the term "single" in two categories: small and large.

Also, [6, p. 168-72] indicates that a single foramen occurs in half of all cases studied. In our work, only the occurrence of zygomaticofacial foramina on female skulls on the left side reached the mark in half of all cases studied.

In all works, the special significance for clinical practice of the zygomaticofacial foramina is affected;

this is especially important for anesthetic procedures. Given the increase in the quality and use of a wide variety of surgical procedures in the face, the value of anatomical studies aimed at identifying the features of the zygomaticofacial foramina can not be overestimated [4, p. 168-171; 5, p. 1035-1041; 8, p. 275-7].

Conclusion. The zygomaticofacial foramina show high variability in terms of quantitative expression; often on the right and left sides of the same skull, different quantitative variants of the zygomaticofacial foramina are revealed. When performing surgical interventions on the face, all variants of the zygomaticofacial foramina must be taken into account.

References:

1. Khalid S, Iwanaga J, Loukas M, et al. (July 23, 2017) Bilateral Absence of the Zygomatic Nerve and Zygomaticofacial Nerve and Foramina. *Cureus* 9(7): e1505.
2. Inderbir Singh's Textbook of Anatomy: Head and Neck, Neuroanatomy, Genetics. Edited by S.Seshayyan. 6th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers; 2016.
3. Aksu F, Ceri NG, Arman C, Zeybek FG, Tetik S. Location and incidence of the zygomaticofacial foramen: An anatomic study. *Clin Anat.* 2009 Jul;22(5):559-62.
4. Zhao Y, Chundury RV, Blandford AD, Perry JD. Anatomical Description of Zygomatic Foramina in African American Skulls. *Ophthalmic Plast Reconstr Surg.* 2018 Mar/Apr;34(2):168-171.
5. Ferro A., Basyuni S., Brassett C., Santhanam V. Study of anatomical variations of the zygomaticofacial foramen and calculation of reliable reference points for operation. *British Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery.* 2017 55 (10): 1035-1041.
6. Martins C, Li X, Rhoton AL Jr. Role of the zygomaticofacial foramen in the orbitozygomatic craniotomy: anatomic report. *Neurosurgery.* 2003 Jul;53(1):168-72.
7. Deana NF, Alves N. Frequency and location of the zygomaticofacial foramen and its clinical importance in the placement of zygomatic implants. *Surg Radiol Anat.* 2020 Jul;42(7):823-830.
8. Patel P, Belinsky I, Howard D, Palu RN. Location of the zygomatico-orbital foramen on the inferolateral orbital wall: clinical implications. *Orbit.* 2013 Oct;32(5):275-7.
9. Mangal A, Choudhry R, Tuli A, Choudhry S, Choudhry R, Khera V. Incidence and morphological study of zygomaticofacial and zygomatico-orbital foramina in dry adult human skulls: the non-metrical variants. *Surg Radiol Anat.* 2004 Apr;26(2):96-9.
10. Krishnamurthy A, Roshni S, Murlimanju BV, Nayak SR, Jiji PJ, Somesh SM, Prabhu LV. Foramina on the zygomatic bone: its clinical significance. *Clin Ter.* 2011;162(5):419-21.
11. Mokryk O, Hadzik J, Shybinskyy V. Development of the method of conducting anesthesia of zygomaticofacial nerve in people with different face shape and its clinical evaluation. *Journal of Stomatology.* 2019, 72, 6:245-251.